

Improved Thermal Conductivity and Structural Integrity in Thermoplastic Composites Using hBN-PEEK Films and Resized Carbon Fibers

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General overview

Material and Challenges (Motivation)

➤ Material

- Polyetheretherketone (**PEEK**), a high-performance thermoplastic
- Extensively used in **aerospace** applications
- Light-weight and recyclable

➤ Issues of thermal management in modern aircrafts

- Increased **thermal load**
- Low **thermal conductivity (TC)** of polymers (0.1 – 0.5 W/(m.K))
- Carbon and metal-based additives → **electrically conductive** – NOT suitable
- Processability & sustainability of material

➤ Polyetheretherketone (PEEK)

- High melting temperature (343 °C)
- High glass transition temperature $T_g = 143$ °C
- Excellent mechanical properties
- **Low TC 0.2 W/(m.K)**

➤ Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN)

- Ceramic-based filler
- High intrinsic thermal conductivity **400 W/(m.K)**
- Electrically insulative
- Layered morphology → **exfoliation**

Bulk material

Layer exfoliation

Controlling Thermal conductivity – mechanism and measurement

- **Thermal conductivity (TC)** is a material (“**bulk**” or “**intrinsic**”) property – ability to transfer heat
- Depends on chemical composition, porosity, density, structure
- In polymers → **phonon-transfer (scattering)**

$$TC = C_p \times \alpha \times \rho$$

C_p = Heat capacity
 α = Thermal diffusivity*
 ρ = Material density

* Hot Disk Method

★ Phonon scattering

Thermal “pathways”

Part 1: Development of hBN filled PEEK composites for thermal management applications

hBN/PEEK composites: Development and thermal conductivity performance

Thermal conductivity values of **12.45 W/(mK)** (*in-plane*) and **2.34 W/(mK)** (*through-plane*) at **60 wt. % loading**

Thermal transport in hBN/PEEK composites- *Role of hBN arrangement, and surface temperature distribution*

Filler amount → **Alignment degree**

Infrared thermography

Heat transfer **significantly** enhanced in hBN/PEEK composites

- For neat PEEK: **elastic-plastic** deformation
- Upon hBN addition, **tensile strength decrease** – typical behavior of particulate filled polymers
- **Decrease in ductility** - absence of adequate interface area for stress transfer

Part 2: Effect of bi-filler Hybridization on the Thermal Conductivity of PEEK

Bi-filler hBN-TiO₂ hybrid system for PEEK matrix

- **Filler hybridization** → two or more fillers in same matrix
- **Why hybridize hBN/PEEK system?**
 - Improved mechanical properties
 - Processability
 - Cost concerns

Synergistic effect of hBN-TiO₂ hybrid fillers on thermal conductivity of PEEK matrix

- Thermal conductivity **enhanced** compared to hBN/PEEK composites (at comparable hBN amounts)
- Maximum T.C : **8.19 W/(m.K)** (*in-plane*), **1.71 W/(m.K)** (*through plane*)
- The spherical & platelet type filler constitute a '**dimension effect**'
- **Anisotropy ratio** is decreased compared to single filler system

Mechanical behaviour of hBN/TiO₂/PEEK hybrid composites

➤ Tensile strength: Neat PEEK > **hybrid compositions** > 60 wt. % hBN

hBN-Aluminosilicate (AIS) bi-filler hybrid system for PEEK matrix

Aluminosilicate (AIS) morphology

hBN morphology

- hBN/PEEK composites (filler pull-out) → reduced strength

Hybridization with Aluminosilicate

➤ Aluminosilicate (AIS) filler:

- TC = **14 W/(m.K)**
- Better **compatibility** with polymeric matrices
- **Cost-effective** filler candidate

Synergistic effect of hBN-Aluminosilicate (AIS) hybrid fillers on thermal conductivity of PEEK matrix

*10B-50AIS = 10 wt. % hBN + 50 wt. % AIS

- Relative weight fraction → **tailorable TC**
- Maximum TC: **7.99 W/(m.K)** (*in-plane*) and **1.78 W/(m.K)** (*through-plane*)
- **Anisotropy index** < hBN-PEEK and hBN-TiO₂-PEEK
- **Temperature dependence** of TC → Inverse relationship

Mechanical behaviour of hBN/Aluminosilicate/PEEK hybrid composites

- **hBN-AIS filler system: Tensile strength** up to **96 %** of neat PEEK polymer
- The higher the **wt. % of AIS**, the higher the tensile strength → better interface quality
- **Mechanically robust** PEEK composites & suitable **thermal conductivity**

Part 3: Screw-extrusion Additive Manufacturing (SEAM) of hBN/PEEK Composites

Screw-Extrusion Additive Manufacturing (SEAM) of hBN/PEEK composites

AM technologies for PEEK polymer

Extrusion-based systems

Powder bed-based systems

- Advantages of pelletized feed
- **One-step** process
- Elimination of **filament fabrication**
- **Cost savings**

Thermal conductivity performance of SEAM PEEK composite samples

Additively manufactured

Injection molded

- **Microstructure and porosity affect** Thermal conductivity
- Presence of **porosity** in AM samples decreases the density

Effect of rheological properties on print quality, and mechanical performance of SEAM specimens

Rheological behaviour

- The shear-thinning, and the viscoelastic solid-like behavior both improved the stability of the polymer melt in comparison to neat PEEK
- **Dimensional control** in hBN/PEEK
- Part shrinkage during AM reduced

Mechanical behaviour

- **Anisotropy behavior of 60 wt%hBN/PEEK** in mechanical performance
- Along the printing direction, the elastic modulus and mechanical strength are typically several times higher than in the transverse direction

Innovative Additive Manufacturing of Thermally Conductive h-BN/PEEK Composites

Part 4: Extrusion-Based Film Production of PEEK and its Integration with Carbon Fiber for Advanced Composites

Thermally Optimized PEEK Films for Advanced TP Prepreg Applications

30% hBN reinforced PEEK films with the thickness of 200 μm

In-plane thermal conductivity increases to 2.040 W/m·K — an 819% enhancement.

Mechanical integrity of films for further prepreg integration

- **Mechanically robust** hBN/PEEK films – enhanced thermal conductivity
- Suitable for **stand-alone thermal interface material** applications

Design of carbon-fiber reinforced PEEK laminated composites with hBN as secondary filler

- Direct **integration** of hBN/PEEK films with commercial carbon fibers
- Manufacturing technique → **film stacking** and **hot-press** forming
- Electro-spray deposition of hBN on carbon fabric substrate → **through-plane thermal conductivity**

Effect of hBN inclusion on the thermal conductivity of CF/PEEK laminates

Composite architecture

- Depositing hBN particles on the carbon fiber substrate creates additional contact opportunities between the hBN-hBN and hBN-CF networks in the direction perpendicular to the heat flow
- **Bulk thermal conductivity enhanced by increasing h-BN interactions.**

- hBN (in matrix or on fiber) reduces both **tensile strength** and **strain at failure**.
- Up to **54.25% increase** in stiffness due to high modulus of hBN particles.

Outlook and concluding remarks

Summary of properties of developed PEEK matrix composites

Main composition	hBN/PEEK	hBN/TiO ₂ /PEEK	hBN/AIS/PEEK	hBN/PEEK	hBN/PEEK	hBN/CF/PEEK
Composite architecture	60 wt. % hBN	50 wt. % hBN 10 wt. % TiO ₂	50 wt. % hBN 10 wt. % AIS	60 wt. % hBN	30 wt. % hBN	30 wt. % hBN film/carbon fabric
Thermal conductivity performance (W/(m.K))	12.45 (IP) 2.13 (TP)	8.19 (IP) 1.71 (TP)	7.99 (IP) 1.78 (TP)	2.52 (Bulk)	2.04 (IP)	5.91 (IP) 1.07 (TP)*
Thermal paths [§]						
Processing technique	Injection molding	Injection molding	Injection molding	Additive manufacturing	Film extrusion	Hot-press forming
Primary filler integration technique	Twin-screw compounding					
Mechanical performance (in terms of tensile strength)	67.58 MPa	82.88 MPa	62.01 MPa	55.5 MPa ⁺	49.1 MPa	424.13 MPa

*Spray-coated carbon fabric
[§]Schematic only - not to scale
⁺Flexural properties

Concluding remarks

➤ Controlling TC of PEEK

- Systematic tuning of
 - Filler morphology
 - Dimension
 - Filler orientation
 - Filler-matrix interface properties
 - Crystallinity

➤ Hybridized bi-filler system

- Cost-performance ratio
- Ease of processing

➤ Multi-processing opportunities

- Contemporary and state-of-the-art composite technologies

➤ New avenues for

- High-temperature thermal management materials based on PEEK PEEK composite films as Thermal interface materials, fiber impregnation
- On-demand in-space additive manufacturing

Light-G-Comp project: Lightweight, sustainable and energy-efficient designs and production methods for upcycled Graphene reinforced hybrid Composites

More info:
<https://light-g-comp.com>

Acknowledgments

Thank you!
Prof. Dr. Burcu Saner Okan
E-mail: bsanerokan@sabanciuniv.edu

Funding Agencies and Industrial Collaborations

Failure surface analysis of composite samples

(a) and (b) CF-neat PEEK, (c) CF-30wt% h-BN PEEK, (d) hBN₁₀@CF-neat PEEK, and (e) hBN₁₀@CF-30wt% h-BN PEEK composite specimens